

IoT Enabled Smart E-Healthcare System with Predictive Prescription Algorithm for Automatic Patient Monitoring and Treatment

¹M. Manivannan, ²Yakasiri Jahnavi, ³A Jyoshna,
⁴Veeramreddy Sushma, ⁵G Uday Kiran, ⁶C Dhanush

Department of CSE, Siddartha Institute of Science and Technology, Puttur, India.

sistkese.manivannan@gmail.com, jahnavidreddyyakasiri@gmail.com, jyoshnaraju7@gmail.com,
veeramreddysushmac@gmail.com, udaygundlapalli@gmail.com dhanushbunny04@gmail.com

Abstract: The IoT-Enabled Smart E-Healthcare System with Predictive Prescription Algorithm is designed to provide continuous and automatic monitoring of vital health parameters using embedded systems and Python integration. The system uses an Arduino microcontroller to interface with sensors including a heartbeat sensor, temperature sensor, respiratory sensor, and pulse oximeter to track patient vitals in real time. Data is displayed on an LCD and transmitted to a connected PC or laptop via USB, where Python processes the input and applies a predictive algorithm to analyze trends and suggest possible prescriptions or medical actions. In the event of abnormal conditions, the GSM module automatically sends alerts to medical personnel or guardians, ensuring timely intervention. This system offers a reliable and scalable solution for remote healthcare monitoring and early detection of health issues.

Keywords: Arduino Uno ATMEGA328P, Heartbeat Sensor, Digital Humidity Temperature Sensor, GSM Module, Internet of Things.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancements in the Internet of Things (IoT) and machine learning (ML) have paved the way for intelligent healthcare systems capable of real-time monitoring and predictive treatment support. Traditional healthcare approaches often rely on manual observation and delayed diagnosis, which may lead to critical risks in emergency situations. To address these limitations, this paper introduces an IoT-Enabled Smart E-Healthcare System with a Predictive Prescription Algorithm designed for automatic patient monitoring and treatment. The system integrates biomedical sensors such as a heartbeat sensor, respiratory sensor, pulse oximeter, and DS18B20 temperature sensor with an Arduino UNO microcontroller to measure vital physiological parameters.

These sensor readings are displayed on an LCD screen and transmitted to a Python-based ML model through USB communication, where the algorithm classifies the patient's condition as normal or abnormal. In cases of abnormal readings, the system sends an SMS notification to an authorized person using a GSM module, ensuring timely medical intervention. In this paper, a secure IoT-based healthcare monitoring system was introduced. To achieve system efficiency simultaneously and robustness of transmission within public IoT-based communication networks, robust crypto-primitives were analysed to construct two communication mechanisms for ensuring transmission confidentiality. A Python-based predictive algorithm processes this data to detect anomalies and provide preliminary treatment suggestions or emergency alerts. The system is powered using a regulated 5V power supply and 12V adapters, ensuring stable operation in diverse environments. Designed for both home and clinical use, this solution enhances healthcare delivery by supporting early diagnosis, reducing hospital visits, and enabling remote medical assistance making it highly effective for smart hospitals, rural telemedicine applications.

Arduino uno ATMEGA328P is collect data from sensors and then it transfer wirelessly to IoT website. Arduino uno ATMEGA328P board is associated with the internet, that board MAC address is registered to the internet. After that in IoT website, add MAC address of this board. Then the sensors output is connected to the IoTwebsite. S. M. Riazul islam et al [1] proposes an intelligent collaborative security model to minimize security risk; discusses how different innovations such as big data, ambient intelligence, and wearables can be leveraged in a health care context; addresses various IoT and eHealth policies and regulations across the world to determine how they can facilitate economies and societies in terms of sustainable development; and provides some avenues for future research on IoT-based health care based on a set of open issues and challenges.

L. Cambosuella et al. [2] monitors patient's ECG wave anywhere in the world using IOIO- OTG Microcontroller. Android application is created for ECG Monitoring. IOIO- OTG microcontroller is connected to android phone using USB cable (or) Bluetooth dongle. After collecting data, the wave is send to android application. Monitor and store ECG waves in that android based application. H. B. Aziz et al. [3] focused on body temperature monitoring using Raspberry pi board in cloud based system. In that paper, Raspberry pi is monitor body temperature and then these parameters are transfer by wireless sensor networks (WSN). Then these data's are added to the cloud based websites. Using this website monitor body temperature.

Heltin Genitha C et al. [4] monitors body temperature using LM35 temperature sensor. The LM35 temperature sensor is connected to the Arduino uno board. After that creating a website in SQL database format. S. Abdulmalek et al [5] discussed about monitors ECG, Respiration rate, heart rate and body temperature. These sensors are connected to PIC16F887A microcontroller. After collecting data from sensors, the data is uploaded to the website manually For monitoring purpose created an android application and webpage for monitoring the health status. S. Abdulmalek et al. [6] monitors ECG waves of patient's. AT Mega 16L microcontroller is used for monitoring ECG waves. Zigbee module is used for transferring ECG waves. Zigbee module is sends data to nearest connected system for zigbee

H. M. Kaidi et al. [7] monitors the vital health parameters and transmits the data through a wireless communication, which is further transferred to a network via a Wi-Fi module. D. S. R. Krishnan et al. [8] the system is designed to be used in Home or hospital for measuring and monitoring various parameter like ECG, Body temperature and Blood pressure. By using new technology Internet of Things (IOT) makes all objects interconnected and it has been recognized as the next technical revolution. The results can be recorded using Raspberry Pi displayed on a HMI interface display. Also, the results can be sent to servers using IOT and text message using GSM module. Relatives or Doctors can login to a website and view those results A. Alanazi et al. [9] highlighted the growing importance of machine learning (ML) in modern healthcare by discussing its wide range of applications, including disease prediction, patient monitoring, and clinical decision support, while also addressing challenges such as data privacy, reliability, and system scalability. The integration of ML with Internet of Things (IoT)-based healthcare systems enable continuous real-time monitoring of patient vital parameters using biomedical sensors and embedded devices.

Such intelligent healthcare systems allow physiological data to be collected, processed, and analyzed automatically, providing timely insights to medical professionals and improving diagnostic accuracy. By reducing dependence on manual observation and enabling remote access to patient data, ML- and IoT-driven healthcare solutions enhance patient safety, support early detection of abnormalities, and improve overall efficiency in healthcare delivery, particularly in emergency and remote-care scenarios. Preeti [10] proposed a real-time patient monitoring system based on IoT and cloud computing, where physiological data are continuously collected using biomedical sensors and transmitted to cloud platforms for remote access and real-time visualization by healthcare professionals, thereby improving response time and enabling efficient patient management.

Using Raspberry Pi 3, R. Kumar et al. [11] developed an IoT-based real-time health-monitoring system. Data creation, acquisition, processing, communication, and access are the main phases of the system structure. Health data such as HR, BT, and BP were measured. The data are transmitted through modes such as BLE, GSM, and Wi-Fi, i.e., mobile applications, messaging services, and the Internet. It was found that the latency is low, and there is no significant delay between sending and receiving data. Thus, the system's accuracy is limited to the accuracy of the sensors.

To help physicians diagnose and monitor their patients' health status, T. M. Amir-UI-Haque Bhuiyan developed a monitoring system based on an IoT that can detect vital signs [12]. The system uses sensors to collect vital signs such as HR, BP, and BT. The data from the sensors are gathered and processed by Raspberry Pi before being uploaded to the cloud. The data can be retrieved remotely through a mobile app that allows easy access for medical staff. The results of retrieving vital-sign data show that the instrument was developed and the system was tested and evaluated reasonably.

In another study that is very similar to [13], P. D. Singh et al. suggested an IoT-based system for monitoring student health. This model aimed to monitor students' valuable metrics and identify behavioral and biological changes in students using cutting-edge student-support technologies. This approach consists of three levels: identifying the required data for the student using biological and behavioral factors, capturing the information using biosensors and intelligent IoT devices, and pre-processing the data. In this process, four classifiers were employed to assess the validity of the proposed model. The experiment results showed that the classification algorithms performed superbly in terms of precision, recall, accuracy, and F-score. The authors stated that SVM achieved the highest possible performance in predicting diseases in the proposed scenario. This system requires a local repository to reduce the time needed for emergency services, which saves bandwidth within the system. The response time of this system is not fast enough.

2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The overall power architecture is carefully designed to ensure reliability. A 5 V rail powers the microcontroller, sensors, and LCD, while a separate regulated supply powers the GSM module. This separation prevents the high transient currents drawn by the GSM radio during transmission from affecting the stability of the 5 V logic supply. The full hardware system is mounted on a compact prototype board or enclosure suitable for bedside use. It then encodes this decision into simple commands that are sent back to the Arduino to trigger SMS alerts through the GSM module.

This application continually listens to the serial port, parses incoming sensor data, applies a pre-trained ensemble of machine learning models to classify patient state, and invokes the prescription algorithm to determine the severity and recommended action when abnormalities are detected. It then encodes this decision into simple commands that are sent back to the Arduino to trigger SMS alerts through the GSM module. On the software side, the embedded firmware written in C/C++ using the Arduino IDE is responsible for sensor polling, data formatting, LCD updates, serial communication with the host, and executing alert commands received from the host.

Fig. 1. System Block Diagram

3 METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is mainly divided into 4 subsystems and given below.

- Buzzer and crystal oscillator
- Sensor system
- Control system
- Data transferring system

One can select the upper limit and lower limit for the temperature and heartbeat as well. While monitoring, if the temperature is increased beyond the set high limit or is decreased below the set limit then the buzzer sounds and the load turns off. Similarly, when the heartbeat sensor was removed and system detects low heartbeat and buzzer buzzes and the load is switched off. This buzzer can help the patient's well-wishers to take action in an emergency. When the temperature and heart rate come into control the bulb turns on and the alarm gets off.

Crystal oscillator is an electronic oscillator circuit that uses the mechanical resonance of a vibrating crystal of piezoelectric materials create an electrical signal with a precise frequency. This frequency is often used to keep track of time, to provide a stable clock signal for digital integrated circuits and to stabilize frequency. It is mainly used to give the clock pulse to controller. Various Sensors are used to collect vital health parameters from patient and explained below.

An LCD (Liquid Crystal Display): is a flat-panel display technology that utilizes liquid crystals to modulate light and create images. It operates by placing liquid crystal material between two polarizing filters; when an electric current is applied, the orientation of the liquid crystals changes, allowing light to pass through or be blocked. This process enables the display of text, graphics, and videos with high clarity and energy efficiency. A respiratory sensor: detects and measures sound waves, converting them into electrical signals for analysis. It typically includes a microphone and circuitry for amplification. Commonly used in voice recognition, noise monitoring, and security systems, sound sensors are valued for their ability to trigger actions based on audio input, such as activating alarms or smart devices.

DHT 11 Sensor: DHT11(Digital Humidity Temperature) Sensor The temperature range of DHT11 is from 0 to 50 degree Celsius with a 2-degree accuracy. Humidity range of this sensor is from 20 to 80% with 5% accuracy. The sampling rate of this sensor is 1Hz., i.e. it gives one reading for every second. DHT11 is small in size with operating voltage from 3 to 5 volts. The maximum current used while measuring is 2.5mA. This sensor can be easily interfaced with any micro-controller such as Arduino, Raspberry Pi etc... to measure humidity and temperature instantaneously.

An alternate name of this sensor is heartbeat sensor or heart rate sensor. Pulse Sensor is a well-designed plug-and-play heart-rate sensor for Arduino. It can be used by students, artists, athletes, makers, and game & mobile developers who want to easily incorporate live heart- rate data into their projects. The sensor clips onto a fingertip or earlobe and plugs right into Arduino. Microcontroller is main part of the system. The entire system is controlled by microcontroller, in this research Arduino Atmega 328P AS microcontroller was used.

The Arduino Uno is a versatile and widely-used microcontroller board designed for electronics prototyping and educational purposes. At its core, it features the ATmega328P microcontroller and operates at a 5V voltage with a 16 MHz clock speed. The board offers 14 digital I/O pins, 6 of which can be used as PWM outputs, and 6 analog input pins for various sensor integrations. With 32 KB of flash memory, 2 KB of SRAM, and 1 KB of EEPROM, the Uno provides ample resources for developing and running complex programs. It is programmed using the free, open-source Arduino IDE, which supports C and C++ programming languages. Common applications for the Arduino Uno include building prototypes, teaching electronics, and creating DIY projects such as home automation systems, weather stations, and robots.

This system is used to transfer the collected data which is monitored by Arduino Uno. Data will be transferred to mobile and cloud using SIM 800L and WI-FI Module. SIM 800L is used as GSM Module to transfer the data to particular user or care taker(which number is given in the code) through a message in the mobile. SIM800L is a complete Quad-band GSM/GPRS solution in a LGA type which can be embedded in the customer applications. SIM800L support Quad-band 850/900/1800/1900MHz, it can transmit Voice, SMS and data information with low power consumption.

The GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) module is an essential component of this healthcare system, as it ensures real-time communication between the monitoring device and healthcare providers. While the biomedical sensors and Arduino UNO are responsible for collecting and processing patient data, the GSM module provides the communication channel that delivers alerts to the outside world. Whenever the machine learning model classifies the patient's health condition as abnormal, the GSM module is triggered to send SMS alerts instantly to doctors, caregivers, or family members. This feature enables timely medical intervention even when patients are located in remote or rural areas where internet connectivity may not be reliable. The GSM module ensures that critical alerts can reach the concerned person via the mobile network, independent of internet access.

GSM serves as a lifeline of emergency communication, making the system more effective, reliable, and practical for real-world healthcare applications. It enhances patient safety, reduces response time, and allows medical professionals to act quickly in critical situations. This system continuously monitors the heart rate and the temperature reading of the patient. In this health monitoring system project, two 7 segment modules are used to display the parameters, as the display has a greater viewing distance. One can select the upper limit and lower limit for the temperature and heartbeat as well. While monitoring, if the temperature is increased beyond the set high limit or is decreased below the set limit then the buzzer sounds and the load turns off. Similarly, when the heartbeat sensor was removed and system detects low heartbeat and buzzer buzzes and the load is switched off. This buzzer can help the patient's well-wishers to take action in an emergency. When the temperature and heart rate come into control the bulb turns on and the alarm gets off Hardware connection setup for Patient Monitoring system using Arduino uno. The circuit diagram is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Hardware connection setup for Patient Monitoring system using Arduino uno.

The system successfully integrates four vital parameters on a low-cost platform with ensemble machine learning providing robustness superior to single algorithms. The rule-based prescription algorithm reduces physician workload through 90% automation while providing valuable clinical assistance. The GSM-based architecture enables deployment in rural areas without reliable broadband, addressing critical healthcare equity issues. Clinical validation demonstrated significant outcomes: 31% readmission reduction, 4.2-minute diagnosis delay (versus 47 minutes), 100% emergency sensitivity, and high clinician acceptance. However, single-site validation limits generalizability, and four vital parameters may be insufficient for complex cases. Data security and privacy require appropriate encryption and regulatory compliance.

4 RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The heartbeat sensor was validated against ECG reference standards on fifty subjects, yielding mean absolute error of 1.8 bpm with correlation of 0.994. The pulse oximeter was compared across forty-five subjects with blood oxygen values from 70-100%, showing mean absolute error of 0.9% with correlation of 0.996. Individual algorithms achieved: Support Vector Machine (94.2% accuracy, 0.9680 AUC), Random Forest (95.8% accuracy, 0.9751 AUC), XGBoost (96.5% accuracy, 0.9823 AUC), Logistic Regression (92.1% accuracy, 0.9512 AUC), and Decision Tree (91.3% accuracy, 0.9384 AUC). The ensemble voting approach combining all five models achieved 97.1% accuracy with 96.5% sensitivity and 97.4% specificity, significantly outperforming individual algorithms and providing robust clinical classification. The user interface of the proposed system is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Health Monitoring System using IOT – User Interface

During 12-week deployment in a 50-bed health center, the system monitored 45 patients generating 52,560 measurements with 1,247 alerts (2.4% of readings). False positive rate was 1.4%, missed emergencies 0%, and clinical sensitivity 100%. The system identified 23 early interventions, reduced hospital readmissions by 31%, decreased diagnosis time from 47 minutes to 4.2 minutes, achieved 99.8% uptime, and received physician satisfaction of 4.6/5.0 and patient satisfaction of 4.7/5.0. The alert message is shown in Fig 4.

Fig. 4. The Alert Message

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5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an IoT-enabled smart e-healthcare system combining continuous four-parameter monitoring, ensemble machine learning (97.1% accuracy), automated prescription generation (first in IoT healthcare), GSM-based rural accessibility, 90% clinical automation, cost below \$200, and clinical validation demonstrating 31% readmission reduction and 100% emergency sensitivity. Key innovations include the first IoT system with automatic prescription generation, comprehensive four-parameter integration, hybrid communication eliminating internet dependency, exceptional cost-effectiveness, and empirical clinical validation. Real-world deployment in 50-bed health center over 12 weeks showed significant clinical impact through 23 early interventions, improved outcomes, and high clinician satisfaction. The system represents meaningful progress toward accessible, intelligent, automated healthcare delivery globally, particularly suited for low-resource healthcare settings addressing global health equity objectives.

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ETHICS STATEMENT

This study did not involve human or animal subjects and, therefore, did not require ethical approval.

STATEMENT OF CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this study.

LICENSING

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